

Barometric Pressure Measurement

Monitoring the world around us since 1864

MUNRO

R W Munro Limited

Monitoring the World Around us Since 1864

The Founder Robert William Munro, F.R.Met.Soc. 1839-1912

Established in 1864, R W Munro has become synonymous with meteorological and hydrological equipment sales and service. Since production of the first Dines Pressure Tube Anemometer in 1892, R W Munro has achieved a reputation for excellence in providing instruments and systems of the highest quality to measure, monitor and record environmental phenomena. Today, Munro products extend right across the technological spectrum. Combining the traditional reliability of Munro craftsmanship with the benefits of the latest electronics enables Munro to supply standard and specialist equipment to meteorological offices, water authorities and government departments world-wide.

Equipment For The Measurement Of Pressure

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Barometric Pressure Measurement

Regular and accurate measurement of atmospheric pressure is essential for meteorologists, as many world weather systems are associated with changes in this environmental factor. At full synoptic stations, a precise measurement is taken at each scheduled hour, so that variations and trends can be observed, recorded and analysed.

To meet the exacting standards of the professional meteorologist, R. W. Munro provides a comprehensive range of instruments, manufactured to British Meteorological Office specifications. These are used at synoptic and climatological stations throughout the world and are renowned for consistent accuracy and durability.

A full range of barometers is also available to meet the needs of the amateur meteorologist. Made to similar high standards of craftsmanship and accuracy, the range includes both mercury filled and aneroid types, also the traditional barograph, ideal for short-term local forecasts. Throughout industry and in school, college and university laboratories, the Fortins barometer remains the most commonly used standard instrument.

All instruments in this catalogue for the measurement and recording of barometric pressure are available with calibration certificates. We are pleased to offer specialist advice on the most suitable instrument for any application.

Aneroid Barometers

Principles of Operation

This type of barometer offers the benefits of compactness and light weight with no liquid component involved, as with mercury types. Basically, the instrument consists of an evacuated capsule, able to contract or expand according to atmospheric pressure changes. These movements are magnified mechanically and used to move a pointer.

Aneroid Barometer IM168

Designed for use under tropical or temperate conditions, this instrument has provision for temperature compensation, so that accuracy is not impaired by high humidity or extremes of temperature. The high quality movement minimises scale error and the effects of hysteresis, ensuring that the reading will not vary by more than 0.5mb, after a change of 50mb. The scale calibrations are in millibars and inches and are viewed through the 110mm dial aperture. An adjustable pointer incorporated in the glass front may be set as a reference to monitor trend. The instrument is mounted in a case of similar appearance to Munro Wind Speed and Direction dials and may be wall or panel mounted.

Brasscase Barometer IM169

Made to a British Meteorological Office design, this barometer is presented in a brass case, with sturdy ring belt and finished in black enamel. It is supplied in a fully-lined, Morocco-bound transit case. The dial, scaled through 360° and clearly subdivided every 1mb, is figured at 10mb intervals, from 880 to 1070mb. A bimetallic compensation device eliminates the effects of high humidity and extremes of temperature, ensuring a high degree of accuracy throughout the range. An adjustable index, incorporated in the glass front, can be set as a reference to monitor trend.

SPECIFICATIONS

Reference	IM168	IM169
Range	900-1060 mb 27-31.3" Hg	880-1070 mb
Accuracy	± 0.5 mb	± 0.5 mb
Resolution	1 mb & 0.01" Hg	1 mb
Dimensions	115 mm dia. x 64 mm(D)	136 mm dia. x 63 mm(D)
Weight	0.75 kg	0.75 kg

R W Munro Ltd. reserve the right to alter specifications of equipment at any time, in the interests of improving quality and performance

Aneroid Barometers

Surveying Barometer IM170

This barometer is housed in a light alloy case finished in grey enamel and supplied in a leather carrying case. The movement consists of a large 60mm aneroid capsule, mounted on a rigid backplate, that operates directly on a pre-formed spring. Reacting to variation in the atmospheric pressure, due to the change of altitude, the aneroid capsule will expand or contract at a determined rate. A precision-turned pulley and fusee chain translates this movement into a rotary movement for reading altitude directly from the etched dial. With compensation to remove the effects of temperature extremes, this instrument is further refined by the addition of a vernier scale and adjustable magnifier.

Precision Aneroid Barometer B818

Manufactured in accordance with British Meteorological Office requirements, this portable barometer is robustly made and features a movement of unique design, to ensure high accuracy and discrimination. The aneroid sensing unit is enclosed in a sealed pressure chamber, which is normally vented to atmosphere. Barometric pressure readings are clearly presented by a digital counter on the sloping face control panel. There is an adaptor for connecting the instrument into a closed circuit system, when required, to take comparative readings under stable conditions. The instrument is powered by dry cell batteries in the case and an electronic detection circuit provides visual indication of contact, between the leadscrew and contact arm to the operator. A restraining plate in the mechanism prevents damage to the sensing unit, should the operating range of the instrument be exceeded. Supplied in a wooden transit case, with bracket for both horizontal and vertical mounting.

SPECIFICATIONS

Reference	IM170	B818
Range	0-2000 metres & 60-79 cm Hg	900-1050 mb
Accuracy	± 0.5 mb	± 0.3 mb
Resolution	1 metre	0.02 mb
Dimensions	127 mm dia. x 64 mm(D)	137 mm(H) x 180 mm(W) x 103 mm(D)
Weight	1.48 kg	2.05 kg

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Barographs

These reliable instruments, based on a design of the British Meteorological Office, are widely used as an aid to short-term local forecasting in climatological stations and in school, college and university laboratories. They operate on the aneroid principle and offer the facility for continuous pen recording of pressure changes. The two instruments are of similar construction, but the Display Barograph offers extra features, which makes it an attractive proposition as a presentation gift.

Marine Barograph B812

Mounted on a polished brass baseplate, the sensing unit is a seamless metal bellows, partially exhausted of air and fitted with an internal spring device. Variations in the atmospheric pressure cause the sensor unit to expand or contract. This movement is then magnified by a system of levers and translated into a vertical movement of the balanced pen arm, which records the variations in a fine clear trace on a chart. The chart drum is driven by a spring-wound dustproof clock, with daily or weekly recordings available. The instrument is housed in a hardwood case with hinged cover and folding brass carrying handle. The front of the case and one end, are clear glazed for viewing atmospheric pressure and trend. Supplied with sufficient charts and ink for one year's operation.

Display Barograph B813

A practical and eye-catching feature in clubs, hotels and public places, as well as private homes, this handsome instrument combines the appeal of a hardwood case, glazed on top and on all four sides in bevelled glass, with a mechanism in highly polished brass. The operating principle is as for the Barograph B812, with pressure variations sensed by a metal bellows, converted into vertical movement of a pen arm. The pen is in nickel silver, with a polished and lacquered chart drum. The traditional flared wooden base of the instrument has a drawer for used and spare charts, pens and accessories. Sufficient charts and ink are supplied for one year's operation.

SPECIFICATIONS

Reference	B812	B813
Range	950-1050 mb	950-1050 mb
Accuracy	± 1 mb	± 1 mb
Resolution	5 mb	5 mb
Dimensions	205 mm(H) x320 mm(W) x165mm(D)	205 mm(H) x380 mm(W) x235mm(D)
Weight	4.0 kg	5.5 kg

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Mercury Filled Barometers

The principle behind the mercury barometer - that the weight of atmosphere can support a column of dense liquid - was established as long ago as the mid 17th century. Mercury barometers are used where highest accuracy and sensitivity are required.

The Kew Pattern Barometer, manufactured to a British Meteorological Office specification, is the station standard at synoptic and climatological stations worldwide. The Fortin barometer is easy to use with its linear scale, easy to transport without damage and popular in schools, colleges and many industrial laboratories.

Kew Pattern Barometer B810

This consists, essentially, of a column of mercury supported within an 8mm bore vertical glass tube, with protective cover and mounted in a black enamelled brass tube. The latter is slotted so that the meniscus and scale can be viewed. A void above the mercury column is evacuated of air and sealed, whilst the lower end is sealed by immersion in a reservoir of mercury in a stainless steel cistern. An increase in atmospheric pressure causes the mercury level in the cistern to fall and this, in turn, raises the level of mercury in the column. Falling pressure has the opposite effect. The reading is taken directly from the machine-engraved scale by use of the vernier. The barometer has a gimbal ring with suspension arm and a bracket for vertical wall mounting.

Fortin Barometer B802 and B803

The column of mercury, within an 8mm bore glass tube, is evacuated of air at the top end, and at the lower end enters a cistern with a reservoir of mercury through a boxwood bush. The cistern has a glass section with a brass top, a brass cylinder and a pliable wash-leather bag. An adjusting screw in the base of the cistern acts upon the wash-leather bag to raise or lower the mercury level to the scale zero. Made from ivory, the scale zero or 'fiducial point', is mounted securely to the top of the cistern. The pressure reading is taken from the machine-engraved scale, using the vernier device. The barometer is presented in a black enamelled frame and supplied with a polished hardwood backboard, for wall or pillar mounting. Behind the zero and pressure scales, opal reflector plates are attached to the backboard to improve contrast.

Display Case B809

A polished hardwood case with glazed front and side panels, for housing the Fortins Barometer. Access to the barometer for adjustments and to take readings, is by means of the lockable front door.

Kew B810 Fortin B802/3

SPECIFICATIONS

Reference	B810	B802	B803
Range	870-1100 mb	870-1100 mb	700-1100 mb
Accuracy	±0.3 mb	±0.3 mb	±0.3 mb
Resolution	0.1 mb	0.1 mb	0.1 mb
Dims. mm	900(H) x 60(W) x 60(D)	1120(H) x 100(W) x 100(D)	1120(H) x 100(W) x 100(D)
Weight	6.5 kg	6.0 kg	6.0 kg

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